

Adaptation, Translation and Validation of Stigma-conscious Questionnaire for Women Undergoing ART Treatment in Pakistan

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Abstract

Aim of the present study was to adapt, translate and validate Stigma-conscious Questionnaire to measure stigma consciousness among women undergoing assisted reproductive technology treatment (ART) in Pakistan. After adaptation and translation, the psychometric properties of the scale were established on a sample of 350 women undergoing ART treatment for infertility in different clinics of Punjab, Pakistan. Age of the sample ranged between 25 to 45 years (Mean=33.50 and SD= .48). Confirmatory factor analysis showed good model fit to the data (Chi-square/df=1.26; RMSEA =.03; GFI =.97; CFI = .93; AGFI= .95 and the TLI = .90). Reliability analysis showed that all items significantly correlated with the total scale and Cronbach alpha was also excellent (.92). It is concluded that the adapted and Urdu translated version of SCQ has promising psychometric properties and we can confidently use it for future studies on the sample undergoing ART treatment for infertility.

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Introduction

Infertility is a worldwide major health problem both in men and women. Due to increased number of issues of infertility, treatment cost of the modern medical technologies is on the rise (Justo et al., 2010). Empirical studies on infertility have demonstrated that psychological distress including stress and stigma are most common among infertile couples (Greil, 2010). Results of studies also portrayed that those couples who wished to take treatment suffered with social condition including stigma consciousness and fear of disclosure of being getting treatment for their infertility (Benyamini et al., 2005; Domar et al., 2000; Donkor & Sandall, 2007; Greil, 2010; Verhaak et al., 2001).

Pinel (1999) talked about stereotyped groups, in which they mentioned that when people were labelled or discriminated due to some social conditions or some negative stereotyped behavior of society, the group members believed themselves as pervaded and this led toward stigma consciousness. To test the stereotyped behavior among women, Pinel (1999) developed a scale to measure stigma associated with being a woman (N=722) to check the uniform reactions of people toward targeted stereotype status, which were expected to be stereotyped by others (i.e., stigma consciousness). In subsequent studies, Pinel (1999) adapted and validated the scale on gay men and lesbians (Asians, Hispanics, Caucasians and Afro-Americans) to test the experiences of women when they interact with men and the beliefs, they have on how men view women. He found that gay men and blacks had experienced more stereotyping and discrimination than lesbians and whites. On the other hand, women scored lower on group consciousness than other disadvantaged groups. The scale tested perceptions of discrimination and the behavioral consequences of stigma consciousness for example, how the women were judged by men and of how differently men interacted with them.

Since the stigma-consciousness questionnaire (SCQ) was developed, many studies used it in various situations (i.e., people with learning disability or mental health issues), other than gay and lesbians to see how it works and deals with daily stereotyped and discriminating behaviors of society (Daley & Schlichtman, 2018). Many studies have mentioned that SCQ is not exclusive to sexual minorities, it can be used in other stereotyped demographics and people living with disabilities (Carrasco et al., 2013). Many versions of SCQ are available, and it has been adapted, translated, and validated in many languages. Slade et al. (2007) adapted the scale for testing the stigma consciousness among people who were facing infertile difficulties and had difficulty in expressing/sharing their problems. They tested the scale on a sample of 151 infertile couples in which, 87 were women and 64 were men. Other than this, SCQ was adapted in a study that was conducted in Spain to find out the negative relationship of quality of life and stigma consciousness among people who were living with a person with disability (Carrasco et al., 2013). Son and Shelton (2011) adapted this SCQ to examine the level of superior intelligence in Asian Americans, and to test the positive and negative stereotypic behavior that evoked stigma consciousness toward anxiety.

Moreover, Gurr and Gans (2013) modified and translated the SCQ in German language on a sample of unemployed individuals (N=179), to see how other people react when they know a person is unemployed. Similarly, SCQ was translated in many languages including Canadian-French (Sample = 32 hearing impaired), Spain (Sample = 280 bisexual), Persian (Sample = 300 infertile couples), and Portuguese (Sample = infertile couples). They all administered SCQ on different a population and all studies showed promising psychometrics properties of the scale, according to their cultures (e.g., Justo et al., 2010; Strizzi et al., 2014; Taebi et al., 2019; Vincent et al., 2017).

Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire had never been translated in Urdu language, and had never been tested on women undergo ART treatment for their infertility. Therefore, the current study was aimed to adapt, translate, and validate Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire in Urdu language and to establish its psychometric properties. In order to administer the scale on women undergoing ART treatment in Pakistani culture, the original scale was adapted/modified, translated and validated. To meet the objectives, the study was completed in three phases. Phase I was aimed to adapt the instrument, Phase II aimed to translate in Urdu language, and Phase III aimed to establish the psychometric properties of the adapted/modified and translated version of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire.

Method and Procedure

Phase I: Adaptation of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire

Before adaptation, translation and validation, permission was sought and granted by the author of original SCQ (Pinel, 1999). In Phase I, stigma-consciousness Questionnaire was modified/ adapted as the scale originally was devised to administer on gay and lesbian women. For using this scale for women undergoing ART treatment in Pakistan, items needed adaption and modification. Phase I was divided into two steps. In Step I, content was presented to five subject experts (one professor, two associate professors and two assistant professors) in the field of Psychology to evaluate the items for modification and cultural adaptation. The team of experts unanimously declared that none of the items was culturally biased or tabooed, so no cultural adaptation was recommended. After taking experts' opinions all the items were modified in the context of ART treatment for infertility (Albarracin et al., 2005).

In the Step 2, committee approach was used. The committee (viz., one professor, two associate professors and two assistant professors) in the field of Psychology, critically analyzed the items and finalized the best structured items and advised to reverse the scoring of some items (i.e., 1,2,4,6,7,9) for clarity (e.g. Stereotype views of people about the treatment for infertility; ART never affect me personally; I am worried that I will be judged in the light of typical views about ART treatment). No item was deleted in Phase I.

Phase II: Translation of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire

In phase II, Urdu translation of SCQ was carried out. Phase II was divided into following two steps:

Forward Translation

After adapting the scale, SCQ was translated from English to Urdu with the help of three bilingual experts (a professor of Psychology, an associate professor of English linguistics and fertility treatment doctor). All the bilingual experts were skilled in Urdu and English language and in developing and translating scales according to cultural relevance. All experts followed the instruction (i.e., syntax, simple language, and original meaning of items) according to Pakistani culture and no item was deleted at this stage. Finally, independent Urdu translated stigma-conscious Questionnaire was prepared after reconciliation of committee of experts.

Reconciliation Phase

In total, three translated versions of SCQ were presented to three members of committee in which one professor of Psychology, one associate professor of Psychology and one PhD scholar in Psychology were included. Best fitted translation was selected which fulfilled the criteria of clarity of words and their meanings. The Urdu version of the scale was also compared with the original English version to assess content validity of the items, and these three experts and they ascertained the content similarity for all items. After all the protocols, finest version of Urdu translated version of SCQ was kept. The scale was used after getting it proof read and checked by a professor of Urdu.

Try out Phase

In this phase, questionnaire was administered on 40 women who were able to understand both English and Urdu languages, and were undergoing ART treatment, to test the comprehensibility of the modified and translated version of SCQ. However, women did not report any problem in understanding the items of SCQ.

Phase III: Measurement of Psychometric Properties

In phase III, Urdu translated version of SCQ was tested for establishing its psychometric properties.

Method

Sample

A sample of women undergoing ART treatment (N=350) was approached from infertility centers of different cities of Punjab, Pakistan by using a purposive sampling technique. Age ranged between 25 to 45 years (*Mean*=33.50 and *SD*= .48). Only those women were included who could read and write, belonged from lower to upper socio-economic classes and had primary infertility.

Instrument

Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire was originally developed and validated by Pinel (1999). The original scale was basically developed for blacked women to see their perception of being women and how men perceived them when they are around. In the current study, an adapted version of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire (1999) for infertile couples by Slade et al. (2007) was used. The modified and Urdu translated version of SCQ in the first two phases of the study was used in this phase of the study, for determining its psychometric properties. The scale was modified for women undergoing ART treatment. Items were (e.g. People who are aware of ART treatment, judge and explain my behavior character with reference to challenges related to ART; People judge those who are undergoing ART in the light of prevalent views about ART; It never bothers me as to how others treat me because I am getting ART treatment). Items response options range from 0=*strongly disagree* to 6=*strongly agree*.

Procedure

This phase of the study was intended to examine the psychometric properties of translated versions of SCQ. The consent form was signed by each woman and they were briefed about the purpose of the study. They were told to answer all the questions honestly and ensured that their identity would be kept confidential and APA ethical guidelines were fully followed.

Result

Content Validity

Table1

Correlation between English and Urdu versions of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire (N=40)

Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire	Translated Urdu Version
Modified English Version	.82**

** $p < .01$

Table1 reveals that English and Urdu versions of SCQ significantly positively correlate with each other. The result statistically supports the content validity of the translated version of SCQ.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

To validate the Uni factor structure of Urdu translated version of SCQ in the context of seeking ART treatment for infertility, confirmatory analysis was run.

Figure:1 Urdu Translated Version of Stigma-conscious Questionnaire (N=350)

Table 2

The Factor Loading of Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Stigma-conscious Questionnaire (N=350)

Items	Factor Loadings
1	.38
2	.68
3	.35
4	.47
5	.81
6	.92
7	.92
8	.89
9	.83
10	.87

Table 3

Model Fit Indices for Stigma-conscious Questionnaire (N=350)

Indexes	X ²	Df	X ² /df	P	GFI	AGFI	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
Model	37.83	30	1.26	.000	.97	.95	.93	.90	.03

The above shown Figure 1 and Table 3 signify the findings of factor loading and model fit indices of CFA for Urdu translated version of SCQ with original uni-factor solution. The initial criteria for the item loading is $>.35$. Overall factor structure show a good fit to the data with chi-square = 37.83 ($df=30$); $p = .000$; chi-square/ $df=1.26$; RMSEA = .03; GFI = .97; CFI = .93; AGFI = .95 and the TLI is .90. For good model fit indices the value of chi-square was always non-significant and the value should be less than 3 by divided it with the degree of freedom (Hatcher, 1996). So, in current study the value of chi-square is 1.26 which means, it is in acceptable range with good model fit. The value of RMSEA was also in recommended range .03 so the overall model was acceptable with the factor loadings of the item ranged from .35 to .92.

Reliability Analysis

Table 4

Mean and Standard Deviation, Alpha Reliability and Items-Total Correlations of Urdu Translated Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire (N=350)

Item Nos.	r
1	.40
2	.67

3	.36
4	.46
5	.80
6	.84
7	.83
8	.81
9	.82
10	.83
Cronbach's alpha	.91
Mean	36.64
Std. Deviation	17.7

Results in Table 4 show the items-total scale correlations of translated version of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire. The results indicate that all the items have positive correlations with the total scale, ranging from .36 to .92. The overall reliability of scale is .91, which is excellent.

Discussion

Stigma-consciousness is a distinct construct that has potential for shedding light on the perceived and actual experiences of stereotyping among target groups of stereotypes (i.e., women undergoing assisted reproductive technology treatment). Studies have shown that Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire is a valid and reliable scale to measure stigma-consciousness in a variety of samples (Taebi et al., 2019). The adapted version of Stigma-consciousness Questionnaire (1999) for infertile couples by Slade et al. (2007) was used for further adaption for women undergoing ART treatment in Pakistan, translated in Urdu language and validated on the same segment of population. In the current study, we produced a local language friendly and clinically valid version of SCQ for Pakistani women undergoing ART treatment. Initially the adapted questionnaire was critically analyzed by the experts to rule out cultural biases, as it is recommended to critically analyze adapted version of any scale items before translating in any language (Tsagari & Floros, 2013). After this, SCQ was translated in Urdu language by following standard procedure. Later on, the adapted and Urdu translated questionnaire was administered on 40 women undergoing ART treatment, to test the appropriateness and understandability of the items of Urdu version SCQ and content validity. The results demonstrated that English and Urdu version of SCQ significantly correlated with each other (see Table 1). It shows that Urdu version of SCQ reflects the content similar to the adapted English version. Translating any questionnaire into another language or culture demands careful methodology, which were followed in current study.

The psychometric properties of SCQ were also established carefully as mentioned in previous studies (Meyer et al., 2003). Confirmatory factor analysis was run to confirm the uni-factor structure of SCQ on the data of women undergoing ART treatment in Pakistan. Based on current finding, a single factor structure of SCQ was statistically supported with good model fit indices (see Figure 1 & Table 2 & 3). Results of the study are consistent with the validation studies carried out on the original questionnaire, and adapted and translated versions in other languages (e.g., Pinel, 1999; Slade et al., 2007; Taebi et al., 2019).

Result of reliability analysis showed excellent results (see Table 4). The results have shown that Urdu translated version of SCQ is compatible with other version of SCQ, translated in various languages (Benyamini et al., 2005; Domar et al., 2000; Donkor & Sandall, 2007; Greil, 2010; Verhaak et al., 2001).

Implications

Adapted and translated SCQ will help to measure the level of stigma-consciousness in Pakistani women undergoing ART treatment, so that counseling plan could be devised to help them in overcoming their perceived and actual experiences of stereotyping causing stigma. The adapted and translated version of SCQ will help healthcare professionals in hospitals for better assessment of psychological issues faced by women undergoing ART treatment. This adapted and translated version of SCQ will open new vistas of research in the field of health psychology particularly, in the context of ART treatment in Pakistan.

Limitation and Suggestions

Only women, undergoing ART treatment were taken as a sample for determining the psychometrics of SCQ, so for further validity studies of Urdu version of SCQ, men and couples having secondary infertility should also be investigated. Sample was taken from one province (i.e., Punjab) of Pakistan, future studies should include a larger sample from other provinces of Pakistan to develop norms and assess province wise stigma consciousness among men and women of different age groups, undergoing ART treatment for infertility.

Conclusion

The results show that SCQ, adapted for women undergoing ART treatment for infertility in Pakistan and translated in Urdu, is a valid and reliable tool to be used in future studies. On the basis of results, we

proclaim the adapted and translated SCQ is not only compatible with the original questionnaire (Pinel, 1999), but also compatible with the adapted and translated versions in other languages.

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